

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH IN THE FIFTH CLASSES

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Abstract: *This article is about the importance of learning English and the importance of this language to the world community. The reasons why most of the population of the earth speak this language are given. Recommendations for teaching this language are given and special attention is paid to the age group, and mainly eleven and twelve age groups are covered. Thoughts were given on effective teaching of English to 5th grade students and some recommendations were given. Solutions to some of the problems encountered in their training are described in detail.*

Key words: *UN, ontogenesis, individual, imitation, conscious, grammar, exercises, dogmatism, culture, tradition.*

In today's developing world, the importance of English language is increasing day by day. Why English now? The main reason we learn English [1] is that it is the 3rd most spoken language in the world. One of the official working languages of the United Nations, it is widely used in many countries in Great Britain, Ireland, North America, New Zealand, Asia and Africa. More than four hundred million people on earth use this language. Therefore, learning English is the demand of today's time. Some people think that learning a foreign language means forgetting your mother tongue. But on the contrary, learning a foreign language does not mean forgetting one's own language, it means knowing two languages perfectly, exchanging ideas. Because we learn and master a foreign language by comparing it to our mother tongue. The more knowledge your student has in his native language, the more he knows a foreign language.

When teaching English to all ages in the fifth grade, special attention should be paid to the student's ontogeny. [2] Ontogeny is the course of individual (personal) development of an organism from its birth to the end of its life. Educating a person without proper training is sometimes ineffective.

The teacher should be such that he attracts the student, he should set an example in every direction. Until the child unknowingly imitates that teacher and unknowingly decides to master that subject in depth. Because we [3] not only consciously choose our initial habits, but also imitate them.

We follow the path shown by our parents, loved ones, religion or school, neighborhood and society as a whole.

Typically, 5th classes include children around 11 or 12 years old. This is the time when children learn to read and write in their mother tongue, and learn another language carefully. We use different methods for students of this age. The methods used by the teacher should be varied.

The students we want to teach have already entered the world of English in pre-school and primary education. He has enough vocabulary to name things around him. Now we need to focus on their grammar. Because they have an understanding of participles, sentence structure, and phrases in the Uzbek language.

He cannot learn a foreign language without learning its grammar. If we analyze the structure of each sentence grammatically, it will be appropriate for the purpose. Because the language organized through grammar makes human communication smooth and free of any defects. 5th grade students have enough vocabulary, we should teach them grammar. Based on my research, I can say that if we explain grammar in the wrong way, it may be boring or incomprehensible to the child. Because not all students in the class are equally interested in learning English or have different receptive abilities. Children of this age are hungry for different games. Such games should be organized to attract all students and make them fully understand the topic. The organization of such games is based on the professional skills of the teacher.

Another way to teach grammar is to use students' imaginations. As Albert Einstein said, "Imagination is more important than knowledge." Now let's use the example of the subordinate auxiliary verb that many people know. We know how to form this auxiliary verb with the auxiliary verbs Am/Is/are. But this may not be complicated or interesting for the reader. And we can explain it in a different way. In ancient times, Mrs. Tobe and her 3 playful named Am, Is, Are. as long as they have children. But if they don't know what pronouns are, they can't help people. Mrs. Tobe tries to find pronouns every day, as she wants to show her children to everyone. One day a miracle happened, Mrs. Tobe found them and gave them to her children. Then Am is touched only by I, Is by He/She/It and Are by We/You/They. Since then, Mrs. Tobe's children have been seen on earth. If it is explained in such forms, we will achieve the desired result. They imagine and remember this fairy tale.

It is necessary to explain and repeat the essence of what we are teaching to students. In each lesson, it is necessary to give exercises to strengthen the topic learned. Choosing exercises from easy to difficult level sharpens the student's thinking and increases his thoroughness in mastering the subject.

Knowing how to organize the lesson will lead to our desired goal. Children studying in the 5th grade are very hungry for the game. They wait for news from the teacher in every lesson. This encourages the specialist in this field to work on news and not to fall under the influence of dogmatism [4]. "Dogmatism, fanaticism is a way of thinking blindly, without examining it from a critical point of view, without taking into account the specific circumstances". Dogmatism hinders the progress of science in order to learn new ideas and invent new ideas. In short, it means to stay in one place.

But constant news also makes the child tired. Therefore, it is appropriate to pay special attention to the concept of norm. The teacher should use the same method or word more than once in the lesson. If such work is done, a strong boredom will appear in the child's mind.

It is necessary to study textbooks and other literature when teaching English [5]. As a result of the teacher's efforts to teach English and the student's many exercises, the English language may not be mastered at the specified level. This opinion is correct. Textbooks used for school in Uzbekistan today do not give effective results. Because first of all to general English attention should be paid, and then information and exercises should be given on the 4 areas of language acquisition: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. In the current textbooks, it is enough to give exercises on 2 directions. The advantage of the textbook is that the words of each topic are given with translation on the back pages of the textbook, which is an achievement of language teaching.

In short, by learning a foreign language, we become observers and participants of the news happening in the world. In addition to teaching English, we learn the culture of those who speak this language, we cannot learn another language without knowing their culture and customs. At the same time, we also have the opportunity to present our culture, rich history and cultural heritage to the whole world. it's good. The complicated process of learning a foreign language should be made easier by inventing some methods. It is appropriate to teach based on the student's interest and aspirations. It is necessary to improve the textbooks and used literature, to make them age-appropriate.

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